

Nicomachus Averaging

Adolf Cusmariu

adolcus@gmail.com

An ancient (and surprising) result attributed to Nicomachus **[1]** is that for the consecutive integer string $\{n\} = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N n = \left(\sum_{n=1}^N n^3\right)^{1/2}$$

Though the averaging method **[2]** won't work to prove this, let's try it anyway for the first three integers:

$$1 + 2 + 3 = 6 \\ = (1+2)/2 + (2+3)/2 + (1+3)/2 = a + b + c$$

Application of the RHS to the string $\{a,b,c\}$ above gives:

$$(a^3 + b^3 + c^3)^{1/2} = 5.196152422706632$$

Close, but not quite.

Let v_3 be the column vector

$$v_3 = [1; 2; 3]$$

Averaging, of course, amounts to nothing more than the computation

$$\frac{1}{2}(I + S)v_3$$

where S is the shift matrix and I the identity matrix; in this (3 x 3) case

$$q_3 = \frac{1}{2}(I + S) = \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 & 1/2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/2 & 1/2 \\ 1/2 & 0 & 1/2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Nicomachus Averaging then is the computation

$$\text{sqrt}(\text{sum}((q_3 * v_3).^3))$$

Do matters improve upon iteration?

The OCTAVE loop

```
for k=1:30, w3(k)=sqrt(sum((q3^k*v3).^3));end
```

shows convergence numerically to

$$w_3(26) = 4.898979485566356$$

even further short of 6, so iteration doesn't help.

Let's continue to the 4x4 case;

$$v_4 = [1; 2; 3; 4]$$

$$\text{sum}(v_4) = 10.$$

The averaging iterator is now

$$q_4 = \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 & 1/2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/2 & 1/2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/2 & 1/2 \\ 1/2 & 0 & 0 & 1/2 \end{bmatrix}$$

and the OCTAVE loop takes a bit longer to converge this time:

for k=1:60, w4(k)=sqrt(sum((q4^k*v4).^3));end

$$w_4(1) = 8.803408430829505$$

still short of 10, and the converged value

$$w_4(53) = 7.905694150420948$$

is even further away.

Now, the general (N x N) iterator

$$Q = \frac{1}{2}(I + S)$$

is doubly-stochastic, so **[2]**

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q^n = \frac{1}{N}J$$

where J is the matrix of all 1's.

$$\text{For } \{n\} = [1; 2; 3; \dots; N]$$

$[(J/N)\{n\}]^3$ is an N-long constant vector with identical entries $[(N+1)/2]^3$; hence the sum

$$\text{sum}([(J/N)\{n\}]^3) = N[(N+1)/2]^3$$

yielding the convergence counter

$$W(N) = (N[(N+1)/2]^3)^{1/2} \text{ for } N = 3, 4, \dots$$

This counter is plotted below in blue, for N up to 100; in red is the consecutive integer sum up to 100.

Let's try a few prime sequences.

For $p3=[2;3;5];$

the iteration

for k=1:30, u3(k)=sqrt(sum((q3^n*v3).^3));,end

converges quickly and yields

$u3(25) = 10.54092553389460$

now a bit larger than $\text{sum}(p3) = 10$.

Next, for $p4=[2;3;5;7],$ the iteration

for k=1:60, u4(k)=sqrt(sum((q4^n*p4).^3));,end

yields

$u4(50) = 17.52319890887506$

again, larger than $\text{sum}(p4) = 17$.

The convergence here is accomplished more easily as follows; let

$J3=\text{ones}(3,3)/3$; then the estimation

$\text{sqrt}(\text{sum}((J3*p3).^3))$

yields $10.54092553389460,$ as above.

Next, for $p_4 = [2;3;5;7]$, the code

$J_4 = \text{ones}(4,4)/4; \text{sqrt}(\text{sum}((J_4 * p_4).^3));$

yields 17.52319890887506, as earlier.

For $p_5 = [2;3;5;7;11]$, so $\text{sum}(p_5) = 28$, while the code

$J_5 = \text{ones}(5,5)/5; \text{sqrt}(\text{sum}((J_5 * p_5).^3))$

yields **29.63241468392342**

For $p_6 = [2;3;5;7;11;13]$, so $\text{sum}(p_6) = 41$, while

$J_6 = \text{ones}(6,6)/6; \text{sqrt}(\text{sum}((J_6 * p_6).^3))$

yields **43.75468228912447**

For $p_7 = [2;3;5;7;11;13;17]$, so $\text{sum}(p_7) = 58$, while

$J_7 = \text{ones}(7,7)/7; \text{sqrt}(\text{sum}((J_7 * p_7).^3))$

yields **63.10212002001523**

For $p_8 = [2;3;5;7;11;13;17;19]$, so $\text{sum}(p_8) = 77$, while

$J_8 = \text{ones}(8,8)/8; \text{sqrt}(\text{sum}((J_8 * p_8).^3))$

yields **84.45903222864918**

For $p_9 = [2;3;5;7;11;13;17;19;23]$, so $\text{sum}(p_9) = 100$, while

$J_9 = \text{ones}(9,9)/9; \text{sqrt}(\text{sum}((J_9 * p_9).^3))$

yields interestingly **111.11111111111111**

Finally, for $p_{10} = [2;3;5;7;11;13;17;19;23;29]$, so $\text{sum}(p_{10}) = 129$, while

$J_{10} = \text{ones}(10,10)/10; \text{sqrt}(\text{sum}((J_{10} * p_{10}).^3))$

yields **146.5158353216471**

For consecutive prime sequence, iterative Nicomachus Averaging exceeds their sum.

References

[1] Wikipedia article on Nicomachus.

[2] A. Cusmariu, 'A proof of the Arithmetic Mean-Geometric Mean Inequality'; zenodo.org.